

From Dharma to Self-Determination: Happiness and Goal Orientation Across Time

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Abstract—This paper examines happiness and goal orientation through the ancient Indian philosophical and contemporary psychological perspectives. Across cultures and eras, the search for a fulfilling life has focused on understanding joy and purpose. Ancient Indian thought views happiness (ananda) as inner bliss rooted in self-realization and dharma, while Greek philosophy highlights eudaimonia- flourishing through virtue and personal excellence. In both, happiness stems from ethical living and meaningful engagement with life. Modern psychology, by contrast, explores happiness through measurable concepts like emotional well-being, life satisfaction, and goal achievement. Theories such as Self-Determination Theory and Achievement Goal Theory underscore autonomy, competence, and connection as key ingredients of well-being. Positive Psychology further emphasizes strengths, optimism, and purpose. By integrating philosophical and psychological viewpoints, this paper presents a holistic framework for understanding how the pursuit of happiness and meaningful goals continues to define human well-being.

Keywords: Happiness, Goal Orientation, Perspectives

I. INTRODUCTION

The idea of happiness and the importance of setting goals have been meaningful to people across different cultures and time periods. Throughout history, individuals have tried to understand what makes life fulfilling and how pursuing certain goals can influence our sense of joy and purpose. Whether in ancient spiritual teachings or in modern scientific studies, these topics have continued to play an important role in shaping how we think about human life and well-being (Radhakrishnan, 1999; Seligman, 2011). In ancient times, especially in Indian and Greek philosophies, happiness was not simply seen as feeling good or having material success. Instead, it was understood as something deeper connected to living a life of virtue, fulfilling one's responsibilities, and achieving inner peace. For example, in Indian philosophy, the concept of ananda refers to a state of bliss that comes from realizing one's true self and living according to dharma (moral duty) (Radhakrishnan, 1999). Similarly, the Greek idea of eudaimonia, often translated as happiness or flourishing, means living a life that expresses one's highest potential and virtues (Aristotle, trans. 2009). In both traditions, happiness was viewed as the result of living a meaningful and ethical life. Setting and pursuing goals was not just about success or competition, but about fulfilling one's role in society and achieving spiritual or moral growth (Dasgupta, 1922).

Modern psychology, on the other hand, looks at happiness in different ways. Today, researchers often study happiness using measurable ideas like life satisfaction, emotional balance, and psychological well-being (Diener et al., 1999). Many modern theories suggest that happiness comes from achieving personal goals, feeling capable, and having control over one's life. The Self-Determination Theory by Deci and Ryan (2000), for instance, says that people feel happier and more fulfilled when their basic needs for autonomy or freedom, ability, and relatedness are met. Similarly, Achievement Goal Theory explains how people's motivations, whether to improve themselves or to outperform others can shape their emotional experiences and success (Elliot & McGregor, 2001). The field of Positive Psychology, developed by scholars like Martin Seligman (2011), also focuses on strengths, optimism, and meaning in life as key parts of lasting happiness. Happiness and goal orientation are deeply connected, as setting meaningful goals gives life direction and a sense of purpose. Positive Psychology adds optimism and life

meaning to the equation. Indian knowledge systems like Yoga and the Bhagavad Gita in contrast, prioritize inner harmony, dharma, and detachment from outcomes, offering a spiritually rooted, holistic understanding of happiness that complements and enriches Western perspectives. Keeping this in view, the objectives of the study are stated as-

I.I. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To explore ancient and modern Indian perspective of happiness
- 2) To explore ancient and modern Indian perspective of goal orientation

I.II. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Understanding the ancient and modern perspectives on happiness and goal orientation holds significant value in both academic and practical domains. The understanding of happiness has transformed over time, influenced by cultural, spiritual, and philosophical thought. Ancient Indian view of happiness emphasizes virtue, self-realization, and moral living, while modern psychology focuses on subjective well-being, autonomy, and emotional regulation. Happiness has become the need of the hour as human being now a days have been suffering from various physical, mental issues. By comparing these approaches, this study provides a well-rounded perspective that bridges ancient wisdom and modern theory. It offers valuable insights for enhancing current well-being practices in fields like education, counselling, and mental health through a more integrated approach.

I.III. FROM DHARMA TO SELF-DETERMINATION

Goal orientation significantly influences behaviour, learning, and growth. Ancient Indian thought, through the 'Purusharthas', promotes goal-setting aligned with ethics and spiritual fulfilment, emphasizing societal harmony over personal gain. In contrast, modern psychology explores achievement and motivation through theories like Self-Determination and Achievement Goal Theory, focusing on performance and self-efficacy. Comparing these views reveals the evolution of goal-setting from spiritual to psychological dimensions, offering valuable insights for creating balanced approaches in education, leadership, and personal development. Dharma in ancient Indian thought refers to the guiding principles of right action, moral duty and purposeful living. Texts like Bhagavad Gita emphasise that dharma gives clarity about one's role and responsibilities in life. Dharma encourages individuals to act with integrity even in challenging situations. Over time, fulfilling one's dharma strengthens self-awareness and confidence in decision -making. Dharma is about being and becoming. In that process of becoming one develops self-determination, direction, confidence and motivation. The journey from dharma to self-determination thus reflects a shift from duty-based action to self -guided purpose.

This study attempts to explore both the ancient and modern perspectives on happiness and goal orientation. It compares how ancient Indian philosophies and present-day psychological theories interpret these concepts. While the ancient views focus more on spiritual growth and moral responsibility, modern theories are often centred on individual motivation, emotional well-being, and personal development. By looking at the similarities and differences between these perspectives, the paper aims to provide a complete understanding of how people across time and cultures have tried to live meaningful and purposeful lives. Understanding these ideas not only allows us to learn from the past, but also provides valuable insights into nurturing happiness and goal-setting in today's world, particularly in areas like education, mental health, and personal development, by grounding them in ancient Indian wisdom.

I.IV. DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

This study is confined to secondary sources, including the Vedas, Upanishads, Bhagavad Gita, Manusmriti, and other classical texts, for understanding ancient Indian interpretation of happiness and goal orientation.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Studies show that happiness and goal-setting are closely connected in both education and psychology. Happiness can come from having personal freedom and meaning in life (Demirbas Celik, 2018), from the benefits of education (Tan et al., 2020), or from spiritual ideas like letting go of mental distractions (Ricard, 2014). Happiness also helps students become more motivated and

creative (Samkan, Talebzadeh, 2011). On the other hand, setting clear goals helps students do better in school, feel more confident, enjoy their studies, and build good relationships with others (Teruel, 2023; Roebken, 2007; Nasa, 2015; Wolgast & Keller-Schneider, 2023). Some studies even show how gender, school type, and teacher satisfaction can affect happiness (Das & Basumatary, 2015; Buragohain & Hazarika, 2015). Others highlight how motivation and emotions are connected to goal-setting (Kavitha, 2022; Sharma, 2021; Singh & Cutting, 2019). Overall, these findings suggest that schools should combine emotional well-being with focused learning to help students grow in a healthy and meaningful way. It is observed that studies basically are conducted on modern perspectives of happiness and goal orientation while ancient Indian perspectives are often overlooked.

III. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

This study employs content analysis as its primary research approach, focusing on the interpretation of conceptual and philosophical themes related to happiness and goal orientation.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Ancient Indian philosophy spans from approximately 1500 BCE to 1000 CE, beginning with the Vedic age and progressing through the Upanishadic, Epic, and classical periods. During this time, foundational philosophical schools such as Vedānta, Sāṅkhya, Nyāya, Yoga, Buddhism, and Jainism emerged, offering deep reflections on existence, ethics, and the meaning of life. Modern Indian philosophy took shape in the late 18th and early 19th centuries, notably during the Bengal Renaissance with reformers like Raja Ram Mohan Roy leading religious and societal change. It further developed throughout the 20th century through the work of key thinkers such as Swami Vivekananda, Sri Aurobindo, Mahatma Gandhi, and Jiddu Krishnamurti, who blended classical Indian thought with modern philosophical and ethical perspectives.

V. ANCIENT INDIAN PERSPECTIVE OF HAPPINESS

In ancient Indian thought, happiness (Sukha or Ānanda) is seen not merely as sensory pleasure but as a state of inner contentment and spiritual realization. It is deeply rooted in self-knowledge, ethical living, and liberation (moksha). Various Indian texts like Vedas, Upanishads, Bhagavad Gita, Vedanta, Buddhism and Charvaka Samhita have its own interpretation of happiness differently. In Vedas and Upanishads, happiness is mentioned as Ānanda (Bliss). The Taittiriya Upanishad introduces the concept of Ānanda as the highest form of bliss, beyond physical or mental pleasure. It presents a hierarchy of happiness culminating in Brahmānanda, or the bliss of union with the Absolute (Brahman).

“Ānando brahma iti vyajānāt”- “Bliss is Brahman”- Taittiriya Upanishad II.7.

It means True happiness comes from realization of the Self, not from external objects.

In Bhagavad Gita, it is mentioned that happiness can be attained through detachment and Dharma. The Bhagavad Gita mentions about three types of happiness:

- Sattvika Sukha – happiness born of clarity and self-realization.
- Rajasika Sukha – based on sensory indulgence, fleeting.
- Tamasika Sukha – rooted in ignorance or delusion.

In the Chapter 18, Verse 37 of Bhagavad Gita it is mentioned that,

यत्तदग्रे विषमिव परिणामेऽमृतोपमम् |

तत्सुखं सात्त्विकं प्रोक्तमात्मबुद्धिप्रसादजम् || 37||

yat tad agre viṣham iva pariṇāme ‘mṛitopamam

tat sukhaṁ sāttvikaṁ proktam ātma-buddhi-prasāda-jam.

Happiness that initially feels unpleasant or difficult, like poison, but ultimately brings joy and fulfilment, like nectar, is considered to be of the nature of goodness. This kind of happiness arises from a clear and pure intellect rooted in self-awareness and inner wisdom.

In Advaita Vedanta, happiness is not a goal but the innate nature of the Self (Ātman). The illusion of separateness causes suffering, and realizing unity with Brahman brings abiding bliss.

“The self is of the nature of eternal consciousness and bliss (saccidānanda).”- Śaṅkara’s Advaita Vedānta (Brahma Sutra Bhashya).

Early Buddhism from ancient India views happiness as the cessation of suffering (dukkha) through the Noble Eightfold Path. It emphasizes mindfulness, right action and detachment.

“The cessation of suffering is happiness.”- Dhammapada 203.

Ancient Ayurvedic texts like Charaka Samhita link happiness to balanced living - harmony of body, mind, and spirit, and following ethical conduct (sadvritta).

“The aim of life is happiness (sukha), which can be achieved through balance of health, righteous living and wisdom.”- Charaka Samhita, Sutrasthana 1.41.

Indian philosophers such as Swami Vivekananda, Sri Aurobindo, Mahatma Gandhi, and Jiddu Krishnamurti have each offered their own unique interpretations of happiness. Swami Vivekananda viewed happiness as the inner realization of one’s divine nature, attained through self-realization, strength, and selfless service. Sri Aurobindo believed that true happiness is not derived from external pleasures but from an inner spiritual realization and union with the Divine. He emphasized that lasting joy arises through the practice of Integral Yoga, which leads to the transformation of human nature and the manifestation of higher consciousness in life. Mahatma Gandhi believed happiness comes from harmony between thought, word, and deed, emphasizing ethical living, simplicity, and truthfulness. All three thinkers linked happiness to inner discipline and alignment with higher ideals rather than external pleasures. In contrast, Jiddu Krishnamurti argued that true happiness cannot be pursued but arises naturally when the mind is free from fear, conditioning, and self-centeredness. All these philosophers emphasized inner transformation as the key to genuine and lasting happiness.

VI. MODERN INDIAN PERSPECTIVE OF HAPPINESS

In contemporary India, the concept of happiness is increasingly understood as a holistic experience influenced by emotional well-being, social connectedness, cultural values, and spiritual awareness. Drawing from both traditional Indian philosophy and modern psychological theories, the modern Indian perspective recognizes happiness as a multifaceted state that extends beyond momentary pleasure to include lasting contentment, life satisfaction, and inner harmony. Modern Indian scholars and psychologists view happiness as the outcome of a balanced life where personal, social, and spiritual dimensions coexist. This perspective is aligned with global frameworks such as Seligman’s PERMA model (Positive emotions, Engagement, Relationships, Meaning, and Accomplishment), yet is uniquely shaped by India’s socio-cultural and spiritual heritage. For instance, Ananda, a Sanskrit term meaning bliss, is still used in psychological discourse to denote a deeper, self-reflective happiness (Agarwal, 2018).

Empirical studies in India have examined the determinants of happiness in various contexts. Fatma (2022) studied secondary school students and found that their overall school experience- including supportive relationships with teachers and peers- had a significant impact on their happiness levels. Similarly, Barik (2022) investigated emotional intelligence and employment status as predictors of happiness among women, highlighting the role of economic independence and emotional resilience.

In modern India, spirituality continues to be a significant determinant of happiness, reflecting a deep-rooted cultural continuity. Kumari (2022) found that spiritual practices such as meditation and prayer contribute to emotional well-being and inner peace, aligning with ancient Indian philosophical views while now being substantiated through empirical psychological research.

Alongside spirituality, family and social relationships remain central to the Indian understanding of happiness. In a study by Demirbas Celik (2018), dimensions such as autonomy, relatedness, competence, and meaning in life were found to significantly influence the subjective well-being of high school students, which echoes the collectivist Indian ethos where interpersonal harmony and community ties are vital for personal contentment. Moreover, the role of education in enhancing happiness has gained attention in contemporary studies. Tan, Luo, and Zhang (2020), through a pan-Asian analysis including Indian data, suggested that higher education contributes to improved health outcomes indirectly by first enhancing happiness, thereby highlighting the broader social and psychological impact of educational attainment. Supporting this, Wallang Pahsyntiew (2021) found a positive correlation between academic achievement and happiness among higher secondary students in Meghalaya, emphasizing how self-concept and motivation tied to academic success contribute to students' emotional well-being. Collectively, these findings show that while the sources of happiness in India are adapting to modern contexts, they remain deeply intertwined with traditional values of spirituality, education, and close-knit social structures, indicating a continuity of cultural ideals within evolving psychological frameworks.

In conclusion, the modern Indian perspective on happiness integrates traditional values like Ananda and Dharma with contemporary psychological principles such as emotional intelligence, autonomy, and social well-being. This blend of ancient wisdom and modern research provides a rich, culturally grounded framework for understanding happiness in India today.

VII. ANCIENT INDIAN PERSPECTIVE OF GOAL ORIENTATION

The ancient Indian concept of goal orientation is rooted in a holistic, ethical, and spiritual worldview. Unlike modern psychological theories, which emphasize achievement in academic or performance settings, ancient Indian philosophy frames human goals as integral to a balanced and righteous life, guided by one's nature (svabhāva) and duty (svadharma). Ancient Indian perspective of goal orientation can be referred somewhat similar to purpose of life. Ancient Indian concept of purpose of life can be referred to as 'Purusharthas' (the fourfold goals of life).

The foundational framework for four legitimate aims of human life are, Dharma (righteousness), Artha (material wealth), Kama (desire and pleasure), and Moksha (liberation) (Radhakrishnan, 1927; Satchidananda, 1990). These goals are not seen as competing, but as complementary, to be pursued in harmony throughout different stages of life. The ultimate orientation, however, is toward Moksha, the liberation from the cycle of birth and death (samsara). In various ancient Indian texts like Manu smriti, Bhagavad Gita, Vedic scriptures it is mentioned that "Dharma is the foundation for attaining Artha and Kama, and Moksha is the ultimate goal of human life."

The Bhagavad Gita emphasizes svadharma- one's own duty- as central to purposeful goal pursuit. Performing one's prescribed duty, even imperfectly, is preferred over pursuing others' goals successfully (Bhagavad Gita 3.35). This reflects an early conception of intrinsic motivation and alignment with one's inner disposition.

श्रेयास्वधर्मो विगुणः परधर्मात्स्वनुष्ठितात् |

स्वधर्मे निधनं श्रेयः परधर्मो भयावहः || 35||

śhreyān sva-dharmo vighuṇaḥ para-dharmāt sv-anuṣṭhitāt

sva-dharme nidhanaṁ śhreyaḥ para-dharmo bhayāvahaḥ.

It is much wiser to carry out one's own natural duty, even if done imperfectly, than to flawlessly perform someone else's role. Fulfilling one's own purpose, even at the cost of failure or death, is more honourable and safer than pursuing a path meant for another, which can lead to great harm. This goal orientation is contextual and self-regulated, rooted in the concept that each person has a unique path (svabhāva), and that goal pursuit should align with this natural disposition and social role (Sharma, 1996).

After Purushartha and Svadharma, Ashrama Dharma and Life-stage goals are mentioned in ancient Indian texts. The Ashrama system further structures goal orientation across the human lifespan, assigning different aims to four life stages-

Brahmacharya (student) in learning and self-discipline

Grihastha (householder)- family, career, social duties

Vanaprastha (retired)- detachment and contemplation

Sannyasa (renunciate)- pursuit of Moksha

This model reflects a developmental view of goal orientation, guiding individuals toward progressively higher goals (Kane, 1941–1975).

Ancient Indian texts also advocate orientation through Yoga and Spiritual Disciplines. There are mentions for disciplined paths (yogas)- such as Karma Yoga (selfless action), Bhakti Yoga (devotion), and Jnana Yoga (knowledge)- each representing distinct modes of goal pursuit that lead to the same ultimate goal of liberation (Vivekananda, 1896). These approaches emphasize inner transformation over external achievement.

Buddhism taught that the goal of life is to end suffering that is dukkha and attain nirvana, a state of liberation and peace. The four noble truths of Buddhism outline suffering and its cessation. The Eightfold path offers practical guidelines for ethical living, mental discipline and wisdom. According to Buddha, “The mind is everything. What you think you become.”- Dhammapada (Verse 1).

In Buddhism, life’s purpose was seen as a process of purifying the mind, developing compassion and realizing the impermanent nature of the self and reality.

VIII. MODERN INDIAN PERSPECTIVE OF GOAL ORIENTATION

The modern Indian perspective on goal orientation represents a complex and evolving blend of traditional cultural values, socio-economic realities, and global influences. Historically rooted in collectivist ideals, Indian society has emphasized duty-bound and socially approved goals shaped by familial obligations and community expectations. However, with increasing exposure to globalization, digital media, and psychological awareness, there is a visible shift toward more individualistic and self-determined aspirations. In educational and professional settings, performance-oriented goals continue to dominate due to parental pressure, competitive academic environments, and the prestige associated with high achievements (Kumar & Bhukar, 2013). Shreekala conceptualizes goal orientation in line with established educational psychology frameworks, primarily distinguishing between mastery orientation focused on skill development and deep learning and performance orientation focused on demonstrating ability and gaining external approval. Her scale, designed for adolescents, aligns with models by VandeWalle and Dweck, capturing the nuances of learning goals versus performance-driven motives. Yet, in more progressive and urban settings, there is a growing inclination toward mastery-oriented goals that focus on self-growth, skill development, and personal fulfilment (Agarwal & Dey, 2021). The rising awareness of positive psychology, growth mindset, and emotional intelligence fostered by counselling, life coaching, and institutional support has encouraged a self-regulatory and adaptive approach to goal setting (Singh & Misra, 2020). Furthermore, access to technology and online resources has broadened the spectrum of career and life aspirations, enabling the youth to pursue flexible, short-term, and entrepreneurial goals that align with their interests and social values. However, these developments are not uniform across the country; rural-urban disparities, gender norms, and economic challenges continue to limit opportunities for many, especially in underprivileged areas. Thus, goal orientation in contemporary India remains transitional and context-dependent, balancing the legacy of collectivist ideals with emerging trends of autonomy, purpose, and psychological well-being. It highlights a generational shift toward more self-motivated pursuits while acknowledging the enduring influence of societal structures and economic constraints.

The ancient and modern Indian perspectives on goal orientation share a foundational emphasis on purpose-driven life paths and alignment with one’s nature or context, yet they diverge significantly in their framing and execution. Both views value goal setting as essential to a meaningful life, whether through spiritual progression (as in Purusharthas, svadharma, and ashrama dharma) or personal development (as in mastery learning and self-growth). Each perspective also recognizes the role of social and moral responsibilities, ancient thought through dharma and duty, and modern thought through societal expectations and

family pressures. However, while ancient Indian philosophy treats goal orientation as a lifelong ethical and spiritual journey, culminating in liberation (moksha), modern Indian perspectives influenced by global psychology tend to prioritize achievement, adaptability, and self-regulation in academic and professional contexts. Ancient goals are holistic and hierarchical, blending spiritual and material aims across life stages, whereas modern goals are often individualistic, performance-driven, and shaped by factors like competition, technology, and psychological awareness. Thus, while both recognize personal growth and contextual responsibility, their underlying purposes, temporal focus, and societal drivers differ, reflecting a shift from transcendent liberation to worldly success and personal fulfilment.

IX. EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study of happiness and goal orientation through the lenses of ancient Indian philosophy and contemporary psychology offers significant insights for modern educational systems. Ancient Indian texts, such as the Bhagavad Gita and the Upanishads, emphasize self-realization, moral development, and purposeful living as essential to true happiness. In contrast, contemporary psychological theories like Self-Determination Theory and Positive Psychology highlight autonomy, competence, relatedness, and goal-directed behaviour as key components of student well-being and motivation. Integrating these perspectives in education can foster a holistic learning environment that nurtures both inner fulfilment and academic success. By incorporating values such as self-discipline, ethical living (dharma), and intrinsic motivation into curricula, educators can guide students not only toward external achievements but also toward internal peace and life satisfaction.

Furthermore, understanding goal orientation from both viewpoints enables teachers to support students in setting meaningful, self-concordant goals that balance personal ambition with social and moral responsibilities. This can help reduce performance anxiety and foster resilience, especially in high-pressure academic contexts.

Promoting happiness and purpose in educational settings also improves emotional well-being, engagement, and classroom relationships. Programs in mindfulness, moral education, and goal-setting based on these dual perspectives can cultivate balanced individuals who are not only academically proficient but also emotionally intelligent and ethically grounded.

Thus, this study advocates for an educational approach that bridges ancient wisdom with modern science, encouraging a deeper, more purpose-driven pursuit of knowledge and life goals.

X. CONCLUSION

The exploration of happiness and goal orientation from both ancient Indian philosophy and contemporary psychology offers a rich, integrative understanding of human flourishing. Ancient Indian wisdom, rooted in the concept of Purusharthas and teachings from texts like the Bhagavad Gita, emphasizes inner peace, moral duty, and self-realization as pathways to true happiness. In contrast, modern psychological approaches highlight the importance of autonomy, competence, and achievement in shaping goal-directed behaviour and well-being.

By synthesizing these perspectives, we gain a more holistic view of personal development, one that values both external accomplishments and internal harmony. Such integration has vital implications for education, where fostering emotional well-being and purpose-driven learning is as essential as academic success. Educators can utilize this dual framework to cultivate ethically aware, motivated, and resilient learners prepared to navigate both personal and societal challenges.

In essence, this study of both ancient and contemporary viewpoint of happiness and goal orientation reaffirms that sustainable happiness and effective goal orientation are best achieved through a balance of ethical living, self-knowledge, and meaningful pursuit, principles deeply embedded in both ancient philosophy and modern psychology.

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